

Study protocol

Active surveillance of perioperative myocardial infarction/injury with robotic process automation: a randomized controlled implementation trial

Abstract

Objective: Although current guidelines recommend active surveillance for perioperative myocardial infarction/injury (PMI), implementation remains limited in most institutions worldwide because of a lack of resources. This study evaluates the effectiveness, safety, and acceptability of robotic process automation (RPA)-assisted surveillance for PMI.

Methods: In this single-centre study, a newly developed RPA model is implemented into daily clinical workflows. Prior to implementation, clinical staff will complete an e-learning module to build RPA-related competencies. During the implementation phase, working days are randomized to either RPA-assisted or manual surveillance for PMI. Qualitative surveys will assess acceptability, adoption, and reach among healthcare professionals. The **primary endpoints** are daily workload (time spent on PMI surveillance and psychological strain) and cost-effectiveness. **Secondary endpoints** include appropriateness (e.g. adverse device events), fidelity, and system usability.

Expected outcomes: We hypothesize that RPA-assisted surveillance will result in a relevant reduction in workload and psychological burden compared to manual surveillance, with high user acceptance and low burden of adverse device events.

Clinical relevance: RPA-assisted surveillance holds significant potential to become a resource-efficient intervention that enables broader implementation of current guideline recommendations. The findings will form the basis for scaling, standardizing, and eventually certifying RPA solutions for broader clinical use and future market deployment.

Ethical considerations: This study investigates workflow and administrative efficiency, involving only clinical staff. No patient or health-related information are used. The RPA model is exclusively deployed in a non-commercial, investigator-initiated, controlled research study, with all steps being supervised and verified by qualified clinical staff.

Introduction

With over 4.2 million deaths annually, perioperative death is the third most common cause of death worldwide¹. Cardiac complications are a major contributor to nearly half of these deaths and perioperative myocardial infarction/injury (PMI) has the highest population-attributable risk among postoperative complications^{2,3}. The 2022 European Society of Cardiology (ESC) clinical practice guidelines provide a class I recommendation for active surveillance for PMI and a systematic PMI work-up in patients at increased cardiovascular risk undergoing major non-cardiac surgery⁴. As PMI most often occurs during the intraoperative and immediate postoperative phases, typical symptoms such as chest pain are rare, presumably because of anaesthesia and analgesia. Therefore, the majority of PMI remain undetected, as active surveillance through pre- and postoperative cardiac troponin (cTn) measurements is not routinely implemented^{2,5,6}. Despite multiple educational efforts, systematic screening and management of PMI has not been introduced in most institutions, even within well-developed healthcare systems. Barriers to the successful implementation of this recommendation include the substantial workload and costs required for the detailed daily review of medical records of patients undergoing major non-cardiac surgery to identify those at increased cardiovascular risk. Furthermore, cTn measurements need to be scheduled for all identified patients and results are reviewed daily to trigger a PMI consultation. Preliminary results showed that a robotic process automation (RPA) model can accurately identify patients at high-risk for PMI⁷. Its integration into active surveillance has significant potential to become a resource-efficient intervention and address the silent epidemic of PMI.

This study aims to prospectively evaluate the effectiveness, safety, and acceptability of RPA-assisted surveillance for PMI in a real-world clinical setting using randomization of individual working days to RPA-assisted or manual surveillance.

Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of RPA-assisted surveillance for PMI in routine clinical practice.

Specific aims are:

1. **To evaluate workload reduction** through RPA-assisted surveillance by measuring the daily time spent by clinical staff on PMI-related tasks. These data will be used to estimate average time savings and personnel cost differences between RPA-assisted and manual surveillance.
2. **To assess psychological burden** associated with each surveillance approach using the validated *Brief Job Stress Questionnaire (BJSQ)*, capturing key dimensions such as job demand, job control, and psychological stress.
3. **To evaluate surveillance efficiency and quality**, including the time from cTn result availability to cardiology consultation and the rate of missed cTn measurements.
4. **To assess cost-effectiveness** by integrating workload, personnel costs and resources.
5. **To evaluate implementation outcomes** including acceptability, adoption, and reach among clinical staff—through structured qualitative questionnaires.
6. **To validate screening accuracy of other RPA and large language models** using medical information which is available on the day before surgery (plain text from preoperative anaesthesia assessment and most recent physician's letter) from a prospectively collected database (BASEL PMI: NCT02573532).

Endpoints

Primary Endpoints

1. **Working time**

- **Metric:** Average time spent per clinical staff per day on PMI surveillance tasks (in minutes), use and supervision of the RPA model, and engaging with potential technical issues of the RPA model.
- **Measurement:** Daily logs from a GDPR-compliant time-tracking software.

2. Perceived workload

- **Metric:** Psychological burden associated with surveillance for PMI.
- **Measurement:** Selected questions of the *Brief Job Stress Questionnaire (BJSQ)* at the end of each working day.

3. Cost-Efficiency

- **Metric:** Estimated costs per high-risk patient under active surveillance.
- **Measurement:** Calculated from time data, salary rates, and additional related costs. Number of high-risk patients extracted from surveillance documentation.

Secondary Endpoints

4. Penetration

- **Metric:** Proportion of high-risk patients screened by RPA among all eligible cases on active RPA days.
- **Measurement:** Audit of surveillance documentation and usage logs.

5. Surveillance efficiency

- **Metric:** Time from availability of cTn result to the first recorded cardiology response action (ECG record which is mandatory for every cardiology consultation of PMI). Time from working start until troponin reorder (e-mail to laboratory).
- **Measurement:** Derived from routinely documented, de-identified system timestamps in the hospital information system.

6. Surveillance quality

- **Metric:** Frequency of incomplete surveillance of a high-risk patient due to missed cTn measurements.
- **Measurement:** Audit of surveillance documentation.

7. Acceptability

- **Metric:** Perception of ease-of-use, usefulness, and satisfaction among clinical users.
- **Measurement:** System Usability Scale (SUS) and an open implementation feedback questionnaire.

8. Adoption

- **Metric:** Intention to use and support RPA-assisted surveillance post-study.
- **Measurement:** Likert-scale survey based on *Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale (EBPAS)*.

9. Appropriateness

- **Metric:** Number of device adverse events of the RPA model (e.g. missed alerts, data processing errors). Further stratified into device adverse events that resulted in complete switch to manual surveillance.
- **Measurement:** Incident tracking and root-cause analysis.

10. Reach

- **Metric:** Proportion of eligible workdays and staff actively participating in RPA-assisted surveillance.
- **Measurement:** Usage logs and staff allocation records.

11. Validation of other RPA and large language models

- **Metric:** Patients at risk for PMI according to a reference standard classification (identified by at least two of the following: manual screening, RPA screening, or independent blinded adjudication).

- **Measurement:** Prospectively collected medical information which is available on the day before surgery (plain text from preoperative anaesthesia assessment and most recent physician's letter).

Study Design

This is a single-centre, prospective, implementation study at the University Hospital Basel to evaluate the impact of RPA-assisted surveillance for PMI in clinical practice. The study follows a randomized design, in which individual working days are randomly allocated to one of two study arms:

- Intervention arm: RPA-assisted surveillance for PMI
- Control arm: Manual surveillance for PMI (standard of care)

Before implementation, all clinical staff members will follow a dedicated e-learning module (6-8 hours) for RPA capacity-building. The e-learning module comprises necessary skills to use and perform adjustments to the RPA model when necessary.

The implementation phase will last 2-3 months (aligning with two sample size calculations of number of days and PMI cases per group) with an onboarding phase of 3 working days per clinical staff member that will be excluded from outcome analyses to prevent learning-curve bias. Randomization of working days is conducted in advance using a computer-generated sequence. The randomization unit is the calendar day, and no block or cluster randomization is applied. Due to the visible nature of the intervention (RPA interface vs. manual documentation), complete blinding is not feasible. However, participants were blinded to the randomization calendar and received the allocation (to RPA-assisted or manual surveillance) at the beginning of each working day.

After the implementation phase, the study will continue with an observational post-implementation phase for 12 months. During this phase, technical performance, error rates, and time spent on technical troubleshooting or manual override will be systematically

recorded. This extension aims to assess the long-term robustness, operational burden, and maintenance needs of the RPA model in routine settings beyond the initial trial period.

Questionnaires

To evaluate implementation outcomes, workload, and user experience, the study will use the following validated questionnaires at predefined timepoints:

- **Brief Job Stress Questionnaire (BJSQ):**
Assesses job demand, control, and psychological stress. Administered at the end of each working day during the implementation phase.
- **System Usability Scale (SUS):**
Measures perceived usability of the RPA system. Completed once at the end of the implementation phase.
- **Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale (EBPAS):**
Captures intention to adopt and openness to the RPA model. Completed once post-implementation.
- **Open Implementation Feedback Questionnaire:**
Custom questionnaire including open-ended items on acceptability, barriers, and suggestions. Administered post-implementation.

All surveys will be completed anonymously (digital or paper-based) and analyzed quantitatively or thematically, as appropriate.

Participants

a. Study Population

The study population consists of clinical staff, approximately 5 healthcare professionals (registered physicians and nurses) who are involved in perioperative care and PMI surveillance at the University Hospital Basel will be included in the pre-implementation phase. These participants will be enrolled for evaluation of workload, usability, and

implementation outcomes. All participants in this group will provide written informed consent for participation in the study and for the use of anonymized questionnaire and observational data.

b. Inclusion Criteria

1. Registered nurses and physicians actively involved in perioperative care and PMI surveillance.
2. Assigned to clinical duties during randomized study days.
3. Willing and able to provide written informed consent.
4. Completion of the RPA onboarding module (for those working on intervention days).

c. Exclusion Criteria

- Temporary or rotating staff not involved in PMI surveillance workflows.
- Termination of employment during the study period.
- Decline to participate or provide consent.

Intervention

The RPA model was built with the openly accessible low-code RPA-software “Power Automate Desktop” (version 2.58.163.25188) by Microsoft. The model operates in a secure, offline environment, strictly adhering to the standardized protocol for manual surveillance for PMI. Clinical staff can use the RPA model independently during surveillance activities.

In case of device-level issues, such as the model failing to open an electronic medical record or lab result on a specific workstation, basic individual troubleshooting (e.g. re-aligning screen resolution, reinitializing the automation, restarting the software) can be performed by clinical staff. These device-level adjustments do not require changes to the core model. In contrast, structural adjustments (such as changes to the hospital information system (HIS), new clinical

workflows, or updates to the standard operating procedures) can also be performed by clinical staff but require the release of an updated version of the RPA model for all users.

Four task-specific automations were developed to support each step of the PMI surveillance process and can be triggered by clinical staff:

1. Patient screening

Clinical staff can select one or multiple calendar days, upon which the automation identifies all patients scheduled for surgery on these days. Each patient is screened for high cardiovascular risk, inclusion criteria, and exclusion criteria for active PMI surveillance. A list of eligible patients is generated and sent via email to the designated user for review.

2. Patient inclusion

Following clinical review and approval of the pre-screened list by clinical staff, this automation workflow adds the selected patients to the active surveillance cohort. Relevant clinical information is extracted and documented in the surveillance list.

3. cTn ordering

This automation schedules the required pre- and postoperative cTn tests for all included patients, documents the orders within the surveillance list, and generates a consolidated overview of all cTn orders for supervision. Orders are only entered for the following day and can be potentially cancelled during supervision.

4. cTn monitoring

This automation initiates real-time monitoring of cTn results for all patients on the active surveillance list. Typically run between 9:00 AM and 1:00 PM, it continuously scans for new cTn results. In the event of an acute increase in cTn suggestive of PMI, the system generates a structured PDF report—including patient identifiers, surgical procedure, clinical diagnoses, and lab results. This report is forwarded to the clinical team via email for supervision and a potential cardiology consultation.

The RPA model automatically documents all actions performed throughout the surveillance process. This includes timestamps and screenshots for each executed workflow step (e.g. screening, inclusion, cTn ordering, and result monitoring). Additionally, all generated screening and inclusion lists, lab orders and PDF summaries of PMI cases are stored in a predefined folder structure (within the same storage folder of manual surveillance documentation) and are traceable by audit log. This ensures transparency, reproducibility, and compliance with clinical documentation standards. Clinical staff can access these records for verification, handovers, or quality assurance purposes without additional manual input.

Safety framework

Each automation step within the RPA-assisted surveillance process is supervised by clinical staff and requires human verification. Screening results, patient inclusions, cTn orders, and PMI alerts are transparently documented in structured reports and audit-logs. This supervised interaction ensures clinical oversight and traceability.

To ensure temporal validation and long-term safety of the screening automation, a structured, multi-tiered validation framework to ensure safe and reliable operation under real-world conditions was developed:

a. Daily internal validation

Daily internal validation is performed using a predefined set of test patients that represent a spectrum of clinical scenarios, including typical, borderline, and exclusion cases. The RPA model processes these cases each morning before active use, and any discrepancies between expected and actual outputs immediately trigger alerts for technical review and switch to manual surveillance.

b. Periodic external validation

A monthly validation is conducted to re-evaluate the diagnostic performance of the RPA model under real-world conditions. In a head-to-head design, the surgery schedule of the

following day is screened in parallel by both the RPA model and trained clinical staff. The clinical reviewers are blinded to the RPA model results at the time of assessment. In case of discrepancies, identifications are reviewed by an independent adjudicator who is blinded to the source of each classification (RPA model vs. clinical staff). This process establishes a reference standard classification. All results are entered in the same dedicated validation database that was used in the peer-reviewed diagnostic accuracy study of the RPA model⁷. If diagnostic accuracy falls below a predefined threshold (a relative true positive fraction of ≤ 0.9 compared to manual screening), an automated alert is triggered for technical review and switch to manual surveillance.

c. Event-triggered external validation

Early validation is automatically triggered whenever structural changes occur in the clinical environment. This includes updates to the hospital information system, modifications to the surveillance protocol, or deployment of a new version of the RPA model. In such cases, the same validation protocol described in section b is conducted.

Data collection and management

All study data will be collected prospectively and entered in a REDCap-database hosted by the Cardiovascular Research Institute Basel. REDCap allows secure, audit-trailed data entry with automated timestamping, user-level access controls, and validation rules to reduce entry errors. All entries and modifications will be tracked to ensure data integrity.

Data will be collected across three main domains:

1. **Quantitative workload data:** Daily working time spent on PMI surveillance tasks will be captured using ActivityWatch (version 0.13.2), an open-source, local time-tracking software. The application runs on dedicated clinical workstations and records active time based on the focused window title and application. Data will be collected manually at the end of each surveillance day throughout the study period.

2. **Qualitative questionnaires:** Staff will complete validated questionnaires (BJSQ, SUS, EBPAS) at predefined time points (e.g., end of each working shift or at study midpoint and end), depending on the outcome.
3. **Implementation and system-level data:** System usage logs, RPA activity logs, and surveillance process data (e.g., number of high-risk patients, timestamps of troponin results and ECG recordings) will be collected routinely via hospital information system extraction, surveillance documentation, and RPA logs.
4. **Patient data:** No additional patient data will be collected, as patients are already enrolled in the Basel Incidence, Patient Characteristics, Outcomes, and Possible Strategies to Improve Outcome of Perioperative Myocardial Injury After Non-Cardiac Surgery: 1-Year Follow-up (BASEL-PMI) study program (NCT02573532).

All data will be stored on secured institutional servers, with access limited to authorized members of the research team. The REDCap database will be hosted in a GCP-compliant environment with daily encrypted backups. Data from ActivityWatch will be manually reviewed and entered into the REDCap records.

Data quality procedures include:

- Built-in data validation rules within REDCap (e.g. range checks, required fields)
- Weekly data consistency checks by the study data manager
- Version control for any analysis datasets

All de-identified datasets used for analysis will be stored in a version-controlled project folder with restricted access, and data exports will be documented for reproducibility. A detailed data dictionary will accompany all datasets for transparent variable tracking.

Statistical Analysis

Previously published data on daily working time during manual surveillance was used to estimate the expected difference under the alternative hypothesis⁷. To account for the small sample size and potential uncertainty, a conservative approach using bootstrap resampling (1000 iterations) was applied to derive robust estimates of the mean and standard deviation. To conservatively estimate the required sample size, we assumed a reduction in daily screening work time from 83 minutes (5th percentile of the bootstrapped mean from manual surveillance) to 20 minutes (estimated value for RPA-assisted surveillance). The expected difference of -63 minutes was combined with a conservative estimate of variability, using the upper 95% percentile of the bootstrapped standard deviation (SD: 60 minutes). Based on a one-sided Welch t-test with 90% power and a significance level of 0.025, this yields a required sample size of 19.8 observations per group. An additional sample size calculation for the secondary outcome of surveillance efficiency was performed. Retrospective manual surveillance data showed a mean time to PMI consultation (time from troponin result until ECG) of 112.64 minutes (SD 64.31 minutes). For RPA-assisted surveillance, we assumed a mean of 50 minutes, corresponding to a reduction of -67.64 minutes. Using a one-sided Welch t-test with a significance level of 0.025 and 80% power, the required sample size (number of PMI) was estimated at 18 observations per group.

Categorical variables will be presented as absolute numbers and percentages, continuous variables as median and interquartile range (IQR). A significance threshold of 0.05 will be used throughout, and all statistical tests will be two-sided unless otherwise stated.

The primary endpoint will be adjusted in a linear regression model for two pre-specified covariates: clinical staff member (categorical, to account for inter-individual variability) and the number of patients under active surveillance (continuous, defined as the total number of patients who did not have all troponin results at the beginning of the working day). Residual diagnostics will be performed to assess linearity, homoscedasticity, and normality of

residuals. If strong violations are detected, robust regression methods will be considered in sensitivity analyses. The effect of the intervention will be reported as the estimated mean difference in minutes per day with 95% confidence intervals.

All questionnaire-based outcomes, including measures of psychological strain (BJSQ), user acceptability (SUS), adoption intention (EBPAS), and implementation feedback, will be analyzed descriptively. Continuous scores (e.g., total or subscale scores) will be summarized using mean, standard deviation, median, and interquartile range. Categorical or Likert-scale items will be reported as frequencies and proportions.

Costs will be quantified based on the number of working hours required from all involved staff and their respective hourly wages. All costs will be reported in Euros (EUR) for ease of interpretation with currency conversions according to the exchange rate of the study period.

Missing data (e.g., due to technical failure of the tracking software or incomplete logs) is anticipated to be low. Nonetheless, we will conduct sensitivity analyses using multiple imputation if missingness exceeds 5%, under the assumption of missing at random (MAR). All missing data patterns will be documented and reported transparently.

An additional sensitivity analysis will compare surveillance efficiency and surveillance quality with retrospective data before the implementation.

Statistical analysis will be performed with the current version of R⁸. To support the reproducibility of our results, the RPA model and analysis scripts will be available in our institutional GitLab repository (https://gitlab.com/usbch/crib/basel_pmi).

Ethical Considerations

This study does not classify as a research project within the scope of the Human Research Act, as confirmed in a clarification of responsibility by the local ethics committee (BASEC ID: Req-2025-01076) on the 8th of August 2025. The study does not involve direct patient interaction or intervention. All data are either system-generated (e.g., time logs, usage logs,

timestamps in hospital information system) or derived from routine clinical operations (e.g. surveillance documentation). All procedures are compliant with institutional data protection standards, and no sensitive personal data will be processed outside secure hospital systems. The only human participants are clinical staff, who will provide informed consent to complete brief surveys regarding usability, workload, and psychological strain.

The RPA model used in this study is developed and operated solely within University Hospital Basel for the purpose of internal clinical research and evaluation. It is not CE-marked, as it is not placed on the market, and not used to directly support individual patient care decisions without human validation. The software is used under supervision of qualified staff, and all decisions remain with clinical personnel. In accordance with Article 5(5) of Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR) and corresponding Swiss legislation, this software qualifies as an in-house device under evaluation and is exempt from CE marking during the research phase.

Timeline and Resources

The study is scheduled to commence in October 2025. Recruitment and onboarding of clinical staff will take place over the first two weeks. The intervention phase will run for 2 months, during which randomized surveillance using either RPA-assisted or manual procedures will be performed. This will be followed by a 12-month observational follow-up period, during which continued workload monitoring, error logging, and user experience assessments will be conducted.

The study will be conducted at the University Hospital Basel and utilizes existing infrastructure, including clinical information systems and time-tracking tools. The RPA model is developed and maintained in-house, integrated into the existing IT framework. Personnel include the study principal investigator, a clinical project manager, IT specialists for technical support, and participating clinical staff from relevant departments. No external funding is

involved, and the study is entirely internally supported. There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Appendices

- **Informed consent**
- **Questionnaires**